

Assessment of herpetofauna diversity of Muzaffarabad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Pakistan is divided into three major geographical divisions. Three major mountain ranges: the Hindukush, the Himalayas, and the Karakorum. The study's primary goals are to estimate the diversity of herpetofauna. The linear count approach was used to assess amphibian and reptile diversity. The direct count consists of voices and physical presence, whereas the indirect count consists of corpses and a group meeting poll. The herptiles were observed using binoculars and a camera; a field guide was utilized to accurately identify the species. During the inquiry, it was discovered that this area possesses a diverse herpetofauna.

Keywords: Diversity, Snake, Lizard, Toad

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INTRODUCTION

Study of diversity is important to know the status of fauna and flora (Noor and Haider, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Panhwar *et al.*, 2022). Reptiles and amphibians are main bio-indicators (Babar and Kanwal, 2021) and are set up in a range of environment during the world without some separated lands. Their diversity are also linked by many wildlife species, but like with many other species, herpetofauna existence is under constant threat owing to division, urbanization, pollution, deforestation, and habitat loss. There are 10,450 reptile species recognized worldwide (Khan, 2006; Uetz, 2016).

A broad study of the amphibian and reptiles of Pakistan has been given by Khan (2006). The intensification and extension of agricultural land uses has resulted in a large number of habitat losses seen across the world during the last several centuries. Currently, however, half of the people population extents in residential environments, and the quick rise of urban is providing a potent new evidence of current deforestation (McKinney, 2006). The impacts of urbanization on local wild life species are similarly severe, although maybe less well recognized. Large carnivore species are usually first to depart from metropolitan areas, substantially increasing the prevalence of lesser predators. Predators then drive small species to extinction, with cascading ecological consequences for the other trophic levels in these systems (McKinney, 2006; Magle *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016).

Because the herpetofauna piqued the scientific community's curiosity, it remained undiscovered in many regions of Pakistan. The majority of the remote research are confined to the provinces of Baluchistan and Sind (Khan, 2006) are the just valid foundation of information on reptiles and amphibian. It is thought that exchange of, human settlements, natural habitats for agriculture, and other developments. Additionally, the amphibian and reptiles are also affected by barriers to scattering such as road accidents (Khan, 2006; Adil *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Kamal and Faiz, 2022). Road accidents cause of amphibian and reptiles' death, risk the endurance of threatened species (Chattha *et al.*, 2017). The variety of reptiles and amphibians is constantly threatened by the negative consequences of urbanization, which has resulted in fragmentation of the broader environment, agricultural development, pollution, and altered natural climatic patterns. Similarly, forbidden hunting and the use of reptile and amphibian body parts in medicine have resulted in the extinction of several species. The current research is thus organized with the goal of estimating the variety of the study area's herpetofauna in mind.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The research location is located in a humid zone with monsoon access. Because of the changes in altitude, humidity and rainfall vary greatly in different sections of the area. Winters are bitterly cold, but summers are mild; winters are followed by spring, which brings with it the flowering of plants. During the months of May and June, the daytime temperature can reach 37°C. The highest temperature in winter lowers to 04°C, and snowfall falls at higher elevations. Snowfall does occur in lower areas (Shara, Gharidupta and Dhani); however it does not linger on the ground. The average rainfall in 2009 was 150mm, with the highest amounts falling in July and August (Figure 1).

The Himalayan mixed temperate forests and subtropical pine forests cover the majority of the research region. Blue pine and Deodar (woods dominate Himalayan mixed temperate forests, whereas *Pinus* woodlands dominate subtropical pine forests. The research area's flora and fauna include a range of animals and bird species, as well as several endangered and internationally threatened species such as the common leopard.

DIVERSITY

The linear count approach was used to assess amphibian and reptile diversity “direct and indirect count”. The “direct count” consists of presence of species and voices, whereas the “indirect count” consists of corpses and a “group survey meeting”. The creatures were observed using binoculars (32x50), and Khan (2006) was referenced to accurately recognize the species.

ANALYSIS

MS Excel is used to calculate the Shannon-wiener diversity index.

Figure 1: Map of the Muzaffarabad, Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During study, data gathered from the Muslims “male” (n=64) and “female” (n=36) informants. Most of informants are educated (n=88). Respondents casts from Muzaffarabad is as; Abbasi, Awan, Raja, Mughal, Chudary, Sheikh, and Sudhan. The peoples from Muzaffarabad having from different ages as; 18 to 40 (n=22), 41 to 50 (n=25), 51 to 60 (n=29) and above 60 are (n=24) (Figure 2).

During the research 18 species noted from Muzaffarabad (Table 1). It is noted that “*Hemidactylus brookii*” the most common (R. A. 0.0855263) species from Muzaffarabad; while it is noted that “*Gloydus himalayanus*” is the lowest documented species (R.A. 0.0263158) species from Muzaffarabad (according in the Table 1).

The “*Bufo himalayanus*” is noted from the study area (“relative abundance” = 0.0592105) from the Muzaffarabad. “*Laudakia himalayana*” is noted from Muzaffarabad (R.A. 0.0526316) from the Muzaffarabad. *Scincella himalayana* is noted from the study area (“relative abundance”= 0.0526316) from Muzaffarabad. *Varanus bengalensis* is noted from Muzaffarabad (“relative abundance” = 0.0592105) from the Muzaffarabad.

Amphiesma stolatum is noted from the Muzaffarabad (“relative abundance”= 0.0855263) from the Muzaffarabad. “*Ptyas mucosus mucosus*” is noted from Muzaffarabad (“relative abundance”= 0.0723684) from the Muzaffarabad. “*Spalerosophis diadema diadema*” is noted from the Muzaffarabad (“relative

abundance” = 0.0526316) from the Muzaffarabad. *Calotes versicolor* is noted from Muzaffarabad (“relative abundance”= 0.0789474) from the Muzaffarabad. *Eublephari smacularius* is noted (“relative abundance” = 0.0394737) from the Muzaffarabad (Table 1).

Figure 2: The profile of the respondents of the study area.

Herpetofauna play an important role in the food chain since they keep numerous pests and insects alive while also providing food for many predators. Herpetofauna play a crucial role in transporting nutrients from terrestrial to aquatic environments, and their removal from any ecosystem may have an impact on invertebrate populations, nutrient cycling, leaf litter decompositions, predator dynamics, and algal communities (Khan, 2005).

Table 1: The diversity of the herpetofauna of Muzaffarabad of Azad Jammu and Kashmir

Scientific name	Pi/RA	LogPi	PiLogPi
<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	0.0592105	-1.2276011	-0.0726869
<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	0.0789474	-1.1026623	-0.0870523
<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i>	0.0592105	-1.2276011	-0.0726869
<i>Laudakia himalayana</i>	0.0526316	-1.2787536	-0.0673028
<i>Hemidactylus brookii</i>	0.0855263	-1.0679002	-0.0913336
<i>Laudakia tuberculata</i>	0.0460526	-1.3367455	-0.0615607
<i>Gloydus himalayanus</i>	0.0263158	-1.5797836	-0.0415733
<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	0.0394737	-1.4036923	-0.0554089
<i>Naja oxiana</i>	0.0328947	-1.4828736	-0.0487787
<i>Scincella himalayana</i>	0.0526316	-1.2787536	-0.0673028
<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	0.0592105	-1.2276011	-0.0726869
<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	0.0855263	-1.0679002	-0.0913336
<i>Oligodon arnensis arnensis</i>	0.0657895	-1.1818436	-0.0777529
<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	0.0460526	-1.3367455	-0.0615607
<i>Ptyas mucosu smucosus</i>	0.0723684	-1.1404509	-0.0825326
<i>Spalerosophis diademadiadema</i>	0.0526316	-1.2787536	-0.0673028
<i>Xenochrophis piscator piscator</i>	0.0394737	-1.4036923	-0.0554089
<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	0.0460526	-1.3367455	-0.0615607
			-1.23583

It took more than fifty thousand years for the world's population to reach 100 million, but it has already surpassed seven billion. While the population was considerably grown in the late 1960s, the greatly enlarged human population meant that every additional billion was added far faster than at any other point in history or in the past. According to the United Nations, the world population might reach more than 9 billion by 2050 if growth rates continue constant. Human population growth is adverse to diversity because it necessitates industrialization, which results in excessive pollution and agricultural intensification, as well as urbanization. Throughout the past ten thousand years, natural vegetations were converted to agricultural fields, and many generalist species adapted to new environments while habitat-specific species became eliminated (Bouma *et al.*, 1998; Bloom, 2011; Altaf *et al.*, 2013). Intensive farming led about changes in land usage in the late twentieth century (Newton, 2004; Purtauf *et al.*, 2005; Stoate *et al.*, 2009); which produced the negative effects on the survival of lot species.

Pests originate from the entire fauna or animal world, including both invertebrates and vertebrates. Pests frequently cause harm to humans, livestock, and crops in addition to being a pest. In the majority of households, reptiles and amphibians pests may contain toads, common rats and mice constitute the rodent pests lizards frogs, or tail-less amphibians, Agama, wall geckos and house snakes are usually measured as domestic pests because of their constant croaking, mostly via their reproduction season, that is a cause of noise pollution, as well as their annoying incidence in huge numbers near to houses. Toxic fluids from numerous species' skins might be harmful to domestic animals and people. Wall geckos and Agama lizards may cause fecal pollution of exposed crops and water, and also devour precious food items, during sun drying. *Salmonella* bacteria are commonly found in agama lizards (Khan, 2006; Adil *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Kamal and Faiz, 2022).

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